

Machine learning assessment of climate-driven variability in European forest fire burnt areas

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ABSTRACT

Background. Despite intensifying fire-conducive weather, European burnt forest areas show contradictory trends, suggesting climate impacts may be moderated by fire management systems. **Aims.** We tested whether climate variables remain dominant drivers of burnt forest area variability across Europe, and whether machine learning models can robustly predict fire outcomes despite substantial changes in fire management over recent decades. **Methods.** We analyzed forest fire data from 22 European countries (1990–2024) from UNFCCC GHG reports, developing ensemble machine learning models using fire weather indices, dead-fuel moisture, soil moisture, and country as a categorical variable representing country-specific factors, including differences in fire management. **Key results.** The ensemble model explained 79% and 80% of variance in the calibration and verification datasets. Despite generally increasing fire-conducive weather, 20 of 22 countries showed stable or declining burnt areas; however, a pan-European break-point around the year 2014 indicates a reversal from a declining to an increasing trend. Under SSP2-4.5, the projected increase in burned area in the representative countries used for the scenario illustration ranged from approximately 1.4 times in the Czech Republic to 1.8 times in Italy by 2085. **Conclusions.** Climate-based models remain robust predictors of fire outcomes. European fire management appears to have successfully decoupled outcomes from climate pressure, but future climate change may challenge this effectiveness. **Implications.** Adaptive management strategies and proactive knowledge transfer from Mediterranean to Boreal regions are crucial in the face of progressing climate change.

Keywords: climate change, fire risk, fire weather, forest fires, machine learning.

Introduction

1 The changing climate and increasing frequency and severity of
2 forest fires in recent years (Jones et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2024)
3 have highlighted the importance of fire prevention and fire mit-
4 igation strategies. For these strategies, information on the likely
5 development of fire risk and the extent of forest fires associated
6 with a changing climate is essential. However, critical ques-
7 tions remain: How predictable are future burnt areas based on
8 climate drivers? And can European fire management systems

sustain their effectiveness under continued climate change?
Addressing these questions requires understanding both histor-
ical fire management success and future fire risk under climate
scenarios.

Improved fire monitoring and early interventions in the
event of fire events help offset the effects of progressing climate
change and generally mitigate fire risk. In the face of climate
change, fire activity is intensifying in many regions, particularly
where hot and dry conditions are becoming more frequent (for
example, Abatzoglou et al. (2025)). Understanding how climate
change translates into actual burnt area is crucial for evaluating
the true extent of wildfire risk.

However, the relationship between climate drivers and burnt
area is not universally linear or straightforward (Burton et al.,
2024), and a critical paradox has emerged in European fire
regimes. While numerous studies have documented increasing
trends in fire-conducive weather — including higher temper-
atures, reduced precipitation, and increased vapour pressure
deficit — actual burnt areas do not always follow the same tra-
jectory. Remarkably, several Mediterranean countries, among
Europe's most fire-prone regions, have demonstrated stable or
even decreasing trends in burnt forest area despite increasingly
arid climatic conditions (Turco et al., 2016; Jones et al., 2022).

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This apparent paradox reflects the growing effectiveness of national and regional fire management systems, which include early warning networks, suppression infrastructure, prescribed burning, and land use planning. As a result, while burnt areas typically increase under warming conditions, they may decline in regions that implement coordinated and sustained fire prevention strategies (Schulte et al., 2017). This disconnect between fire-prone weather and observed fire outcomes highlights the need for a modeling framework that integrates both climatic drivers and the effectiveness of national fire management systems when assessing and projecting wildfire risk across Europe.

Data-driven methods, particularly machine learning ensemble approaches, offer considerable promise for this task: they can quantify the relative importance of climate variables while capturing complex, nonlinear interactions between fire drivers and outcomes, and they provide operational tools for fire management agencies to project future fire risk under climate scenarios.

Moreover, the role of climate as a fundamental driver of fire dynamics remains evident, particularly through the fire weather index (FWI, Wagner (1987)), relative humidity and/or vapour pressure deficit (VPD), and dead fuel moisture content (DFMC, de Dios et al. (2015)). These variables are widely used in fire risk assessment and have shown high predictive power for fire occurrence and spread (Venäläinen et al., 2014; Resco de Dios et al., 2021; Kang et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2023; Nagavciuc et al., 2024). Remote-sensing observations complement this climate-based framework by providing spatially explicit and temporally consistent records of actual fire activity across forested landscapes.

There is a range of remote-sensing approaches to estimate burnt forest areas from properties applicable on a fine time scale to assess the spread and development of forest fires locally (Siljander, 2009; Pessôa et al., 2020). While remote sensing techniques provide critical data for mapping burnt areas and tracking fire events at high spatial and temporal resolutions, there is increasing demand for scalable statistical models capable of capturing long-term patterns and enabling comparative fire risk assessments at national to continental levels. Such approaches are particularly important for policy-relevant fire risk assessments in Europe, where strong gradients in climate, forest composition, and land-use governance require harmonized yet flexible modeling strategies.

In response to this need, we propose a climate-driven ensemble modeling framework that incorporates fire-relevant biophysical predictors and machine learning techniques to estimate burnt forest area across 22 European countries, analyzing fire patterns at a country to regional scales across the European gradients.

The central hypothesis guiding this study is that climate-related drivers have remained the dominant determinants of burnt forest area variability in Europe since 1990, despite substantial changes in fire management and other country-specific factors. We ask whether climate-based statistical models remain

sufficiently robust in a changing technological and climatic landscape to inform practical, forward-looking wildfire risk assessments. To explore this question, we analyze the observed forest fires in 22 European countries, using the burnt forest area information reported in the national GHG emission inventories to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), combined with climate-based drivers and forest resource information.

These specific objectives were defined as follows: i. To evaluate the robustness of climate-based statistical models for predicting burnt forest area across European countries for the period of 1990–2024; ii. To test the applicability of such models for projecting future forest fire risk expressed as the Burnt Forest Area Index (BFAI) under evolving climate scenarios for the remainder of the 21st century.

Methods

Project domain and temporal scale

The analyses carried out for this study included 22 European countries: Austria (AUT), Belgium (BEL), Bulgaria (BGR), Switzerland (CHE), Czech Republic (CZE), Germany (DEU), Denmark (DNK), Spain (ESP), Finland (FIN), France (FRA), Greece (GRC), Croatia (HRV), Italy (ITA), Lithuania (LTU), Latvia (LVA), Norway (NOR), Poland (POL), Portugal (PRT), Romania (ROU), Slovakia (SVK), Slovenia (SVN), and Sweden (SWE). This selection represents a broad South–North European gradient (Fig. 1). A larger set of countries was initially considered. Countries with a total national area below 10,000 km² were excluded, as their limited spatial extent compromises the representativeness of country-level fire statistics; this criterion disqualified Malta, Cyprus, Liechtenstein, and Luxembourg. Five additional countries present in national greenhouse gas inventory reports (Section Source data below) were excluded for data availability or reporting reasons: the United Kingdom and Hungary report biomass burnt rather than burnt area, which does not provide the area-based metric required here; Estonia and Ireland report no fire occurrences throughout the study period; and the Netherlands reports a constant burnt forest area value across all years, rendering the data unsuitable for trend and predictive analyses. The assembled dataset covers country-level burnt forest areas from 1990 to 2024 at an annual resolution.

Source data on forest fires and forest resources

Data on forest area (kha, annual) and fire area (ha/year) attributed to forestland were taken from the Common Reporting Tables (CRT), which are a mandatory part of the national inventory submissions to UNFCCC (UNFCCC, 2026), together with the National Inventory Report (NIR) texts (<https://www.unfccc.int>; accessed 18 April 2026). We also checked the fire

Fig. 1. Analyzed domain of the study, including 22 European countries.

area data from the European Forest Fire Information System (European Commission, 2026), which do not fully correspond to the UNFCCC data. Therefore, UNFCCC data were used exclusively in this study, as reported fires are attributed to forest land, and all NIRs are regularly verified during the UNFCCC review process. In addition to the burnt forest area, we also collected the extent of forest area per country from the same CRT tables. The main dependent variable was the annual burnt forest area, expressed as a fraction related to 1000 ha (kha) of national forest area, hereafter the Burnt Forest Area Index (BFAI, ha/kha). This dependent variable is shown in Fig. 2, both for the entire dataset and for specific subsets, as described in Section Data split for analysis below. Finally, to analyze the possible effects of forest tree species composition, we used a tree species map for Europe (Brus et al., 2012). This map provides gridded (1 × 1 km) information on 20 tree species groups in Europe. It was overlaid on the 22 analyzed European countries, and the share of aggregated broadleaved, coniferous, and specifically pines species groups was retrieved. This information served as additional independent variables alongside the climatic and climate-related indices described below.

Forest fire-related indices

The predictor set comprised four groups of fire-relevant climate and land-surface indices, all derived from daily data. Fire weather was represented by the Fire Weather Index (Wagner, 1987), used both as a mean intensity index and as counts of days exceeding successive danger-class thresholds (Kudláčková et al., 2024). Fuel state was characterised by the 10-hour

dead fuel moisture content (Bradshaw et al., 1983), and atmospheric moisture demand by the vapour pressure deficit (VPD), obtained from daily mean temperature and relative humidity through the Clausius–Clapeyron relation. Soil-water status was described by three drought indices – available water in relative units (AWR), available water percentile (AWP), and available water deficit (AWD) – evaluated for the 0–10 and 0–40 cm profiles using the SoilClim soil-water balance model (Hlavinka et al., 2011; Trnka et al., 2020). Together, these indices form eight families (I–VIII) comprising 18 base variables, whose codes, definitions, and units are listed in Table 1.

The daily indices were aggregated to seasonal sub-periods because burnt forest area reflects fire-conductive conditions accumulated over weeks to months rather than responding to individual days. Two warm-season windows – March–October (MAMJJASO) and the narrower April–September (AMJJAS) – represent in-season fire weather, spanning the broad European fire season and its mid-summer core, whereas two cool-season windows – October–March (ONDJFM) and November–February (NDJF) – capture antecedent soil-water recharge and overwintering fuel moisture that condition dryness entering the subsequent fire season. Each of the 18 base variables was therefore expressed over five temporal windows (the full year and these four sub-periods), yielding 90 climate predictors; together with three time-invariant forest-composition shares (broadleaved, coniferous, and pine) and country as a categorical predictor, this gave 94 candidate predictors. The windows were deliberately overlapped so that the feature-selection procedure could identify the most informative aggregation period for each predictor, rather than imposing a single fixed fire-season definition across the strong South–North gradient in fire seasonality (Bedia et al., 2018; Turco et al., 2019); redundancy among the overlapping windows was subsequently removed during feature selection.

The AWP, AWD and AWR were calculated following Hlavinka et al. (2011) and Trnka et al. (2020). For each of the 18 variables belonging to groups I–VIII, daily values were aggregated over the full year and four seasonal windows: March–October (MAMJJASO), April–September (AMJJAS), October–March (ONDJFM), and November–February (NDJF). This resulted in 90 climate-related predictor variables, which were considered in the statistical analysis together with the shares of coniferous (or broadleaved), and pine forests, treated as time-invariant country-level characteristics. Finally, country was included as a categorical predictor to account for country-specific factors not explicitly represented by the climatic and forest-composition variables. All candidate predictors and their definitions are summarised in Table 1.

Data split for analysis

For the analysis, the input data were split into calibration and verification datasets, representing 2/3 and 1/3 of the input data, respectively. The calibration dataset included the first and second years of each 3-year, non-overlapping block within

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Fig. 2. Annual burnt forest area index (BFAI) of the 22 European countries for the 1990–2024 period, with countries ordered by median BFAI from highest (PRT) to lowest (DNK) in both panels. (A) Box plots (with outliers beyond 1.5× the interquartile range shown by points) distinguishing the calibration, verification, and total (entire) datasets; the *y*-axis is on a log₁₀ scale. (B) Per-country mean (open symbols) and median (filled symbols) of the entire dataset on a linear *y*-axis; the gap between the mean and median reflects the within-country distributional skewness.

Table 1 Definition of the 18 base predictor variables used to model the Burnt Forest Area Index (BFAI), grouped into eight index families (I–VIII).

Group	Variable code	Description	Unit
I	FWI_DI	Mean Fire Weather Index; dimensionless index of potential fire intensity from daily temperature, relative humidity, wind speed, and precipitation	–
II	FWI_3+, FWI_4+, FWI_5+, FWI_6	Number of days with FWI above danger-class thresholds 3–6 (3, moderate; 6, extreme)	days
III	DFMC10H	Mean 10-hour dead fuel moisture content	%
IV	DFMC10H_u10, _u8, _u6, _u4, _u2	Number of days with 10-hour dead fuel moisture below 10, 8, 6, 4, and 2%	days
V	VPD	Vapour pressure deficit from mean daily temperature and relative humidity (Clausius–Clapeyron relation)	kPa
VI	AWR-10_u30, AWR-40_u30	Available water in relative units (AWR): number of days with AWR below 30% in the 0–10 and 0–40 cm soil profiles, respectively	days
VII	AWP0-40_S2+, S3+, S4+	Available water percentile (AWP): soil drought intensity, the number of days on which AWR in the 0–40 cm profile fell below percentile thresholds of its reference distribution (moderate, S2+, AWR < 10th percentile; severe, S3+, < 5th; exceptional, S4+, < 2nd), where the reference for each calendar day is built from a ±10-day window over 1981–2020	days
VIII	AWD0-40_sum	Available water deficit (AWD): soil moisture deficit in the 0–40 cm profile, calculated for each day as the difference between the actual water content and its 50th percentile over the 1981–2020 reference (a ±10-day window centred on the calendar day)	mm

Note. Each base variable was aggregated over the full year and four sub-periods (MAMJJASO, AMJJAS, ONDJFM, NDJF). Three time-invariant forest-composition shares (broadleaved, coniferous, and pine) and country (categorical) were also included as predictors.

the analyzed period from 1990 to 2024, while the verification dataset consisted of every third year within those blocks. The resulting values of the dependent variable BFAI for the calibration, verification, and entire datasets are shown in Fig. 2. The Kruskal–Wallis test confirmed no significant differences in BFAI distributions between calibration and verification datasets across all countries ($p > 0.05$).

Testing country and pan-European trends in BFAI

Temporal trends in annual BFAI were assessed for each country using linear regression and the non-parametric Mann–Kendall test. The regression slope ($\text{ha kha}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}$) quantified trend magnitude, while the Mann–Kendall test assessed significance without assuming normality of residuals. A trend was classified as decreasing or increasing only when both tests indicated significance at $p < 0.05$ with consistent direction. Cases where only one test reached significance were classified as likely decreasing or likely increasing accordingly. All remaining cases were classified as stable.

To examine whether the pan-European fire trend is characterised by distinct phases, a breakpoint analysis was conducted on a forest-area weighted aggregate BFAI (hereafter ABFAI), computed as the weighted mean of country-level BFAI across all 22 countries for each year 1990–2024, with national forest area (kha) as weights. All analyses were performed on log-transformed ABFAI to address positive skewness. The breakpoint year was identified using a two-stage procedure: a grid search fitted piecewise linear regressions for each candidate breakpoint year within 1997–2018 (ensuring a minimum of seven years in each segment), and the year minimising the residual sum of squares was subsequently refined using the `segmented` R package (Muggeo, 2003). Non-parametric Mann–Kendall tests with Sen’s slope were then applied to the full series and to the pre- and post-break sub-series to assess the significance and magnitude of each phase.

Machine learning approach for estimating the BFAI

Several statistical approaches were used to test whether the BFAI is predictable on the basis of fire weather variables and basic parameters, such as country and forest type. All 22 countries spanning a large gradient of environmental conditions across Europe were used for this analysis. Owing to the non-normal distribution of the BFAI across all countries, the data were log-transformed before all analyses.

Feature selection and dimensionality reduction

Given the high dimensionality of the predictor variables (*cf.* ‘Forest fire-related indices’ subsection), a multistep feature selection procedure was implemented.

1. Correlation filtering was applied to remove multicollinear predictors. Variables with pairwise correlation coefficients

exceeding 0.75 were examined, and in each highly correlated pair, the variables with weaker correlations to the response variable were discarded. This step left 12 out of the original 94 predictors.

2. Boruta selection (Kursa and Rudnicki, 2010), an algorithm that identifies all relevant features by comparing their importance to that of randomized shadow variables, was applied using 10-fold cross-validation. Predictors selected in at least five out of ten folds were retained. This step ensured robust and objective identification of 10 consistently important features.
3. Recursive feature elimination was conducted using random forests to rank variable importance (Kuhn and Johnson, 2013).

Model specification and preprocessing strategies

A total of 12 regression algorithms were configured using the `tidymodels` framework (Kuhn and Wickham, 2020; Kuhn and Silge, 2022). These included:

- Linear models: Generalized Linear Model (GLM) and Elastic Net.
- Flexible regression: Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines (MARS).
- Kernel-based methods: Support vector machines with linear, polynomial, and radial kernels,
- Tree-based models: Random Forest, Bagged Trees, Classification and Regression Trees (CART), and Cubist.
- Boosting and additive models: XGBoost and Bayesian Additive Regression Trees (BART).
- Artificial neural networks: Multilayer Perceptron (MLP).

Each algorithm was combined with one of three preprocessing strategies: (i) no preprocessing, (ii) normalization of numerical predictors, or (iii) polynomial expansion and interaction terms among numeric features.

Country was included as a categorical predictor using likelihood encoding based on a logistic regression fitted to the response variable. This approach preserves ordinal relationships between the country and the outcome while avoiding the increase in dimensionality of one-hot encoding.

Workflows combining preprocessing and model specification were constructed and stored for tuning.

Model tuning and evaluation

Two hyperparameter tuning strategies were employed to ensure both robustness and computational efficiency. First, a grid search method with a fixed grid of 50 parameter combinations per model was used. Second, a racing (ANOVA) method with an early-stopping algorithm was used to evaluate up to 100 configurations per model. The inclusions of both methods allowed for cross-verification of optimal model settings and ensured that the selected configurations were not artifacts of any single tuning strategy. Tuning was performed using 10-fold cross-validation on the calibration dataset. Models were ranked using the root

mean square error (RMSE), and the best-performing configuration for each model was selected. The performance was evaluated separately on the calibration and verification datasets. Predictions were generated using the finalized models, and performance metrics (RMSE and R^2) were computed to assess model accuracy and generalizability.

Ensemble model construction

To improve predictive robustness, an ensemble model was constructed using stacked generalization. Predictions from the top-performing individual models were combined via penalized linear regression (stacking). The stacking coefficients were optimized using cross-validation, and the ensemble process was repeated 20 times with varying seeds to ensure stability. The configuration yielding the lowest calibration RMSE was selected as the final ensemble model.

Because penalized regression does not force just a single configuration per algorithm, multiple tuned variants of the same model type might be retained in the final stack if they provide complementary predictive information.

Projection of the BFAI

For a detailed examination of the 21st-century climate under socioeconomic development conditions as represented by the SSP2-4.5 scenario, we employed the most recent CMIP6 global climate model (GCM) projections (Eyring et al., 2016; O'Neill et al., 2016). Daily data from six GCMs were sourced from the Earth System Grid Federation (Cinquini et al., 2014), with most simulations at a nominal 100 km resolution, one model at 50 km, and a subset at a coarser 250 km resolution. Historical simulations together with multiple SSP scenarios were used to generate future climate projections. Although projections were generated for multiple SSP scenarios, only SSP2-4.5 results are presented and discussed in detail. The E-OBS gridded observational dataset (version 31.0e; Cornes et al., 2018) was used as the baseline climate dataset. The climate variables considered included daily minimum, maximum, and mean temperatures, global radiation, relative humidity, wind speed, and precipitation. The selected models included CMCC-ESM2, EC-EARTH, GFDL-ESM4, MPI-ESM1-2-HR, MRI-ESM2-0, and TAIESM1. Owing to their spatial resolution, GCM simulations are not directly applicable for assessing localized impacts. Therefore, either systematic bias correction or transformation of the observed series is necessary. We applied the "delta method", which aligns changes in the observed and transformed series with those in the climate model simulations. For daily resolution analysis, we employed the advanced delta change method (van Pelt et al., 2012; Kraaijenbrink and colleagues, 2013), which accommodates variability changes, enabling differential changes in extremes relative to the mean. This approach also adjusts for systematic simulation errors in precipitation, whereas temperature transformations, which are linear, are unaffected by systematic error. Other meteorological variables (solar radiation, relative humidity, and wind speed) are modified by multiplication using

a ratio of standard deviations for the control and scenario periods in the climate model simulations.

The period 1985–2014 was selected as the baseline period for the ADC transformation. Using this baseline period, four future time blocks were created: 2015–2044 (referred to as "2030"), 2035–2064 ("2050"), 2055–2084 ("2070"), and 2070–2099 ("2085"). These periods overlap, allowing for smoother transitions across the projected timelines.

The final ensemble model and selected individual models were applied to future climate scenario data for all analysed countries to assess the BFAI expected in the coming decades. This provided additional insights into the coherence of the projected results by the independent estimation approaches. LOESS smoothing was used to visualize projected BFAI trends across periods and the mean of climate models. To illustrate projected responses across contrasting European climatic conditions, climate-scenario results are presented for Sweden, Czech Republic, and Italy, representing northern, central, and southern Europe, respectively.

Results

Observed trends in burnt forest areas

Forest fire trends were analyzed for 22 European countries using BFAI data from 1990–2024 (Fig. 2). Our results present a counterpoint to the broader global trends of increasing burnt forest areas identified by Jones et al. (2024). Specifically, of the 22 European countries analyzed, 13 showed no significant trend in the BFAI, while two countries (Lithuania and Poland) showed a confirmed, significantly decreasing trend. Romania was the only country with a significantly increasing BFAI (Table 2; Fig. 3). Further six countries showed a likely trend based on passing one significant test: five with a likely decreasing trend (Belgium, Switzerland, Spain, Italy, and Slovenia) and one with a likely increasing trend (Sweden). Portugal has the highest values and variability in the BFAI, followed by Spain and Mediterranean countries, including Greece, Croatia, and Italy. As expected, the least burnt areas are found in Austria and the Nordic and temperate countries of northern Europe.

Pan-European trend break-point

Beyond the country-level trends, the forest-area-weighted pan-European Aggregate Burnt Forest Area Index (ABFAI) followed a non-monotonic trajectory over the study period. Piecewise regression located a structural break-point in 2014 (Fig. 4): the ABFAI declined significantly over 1990–2014 (Mann–Kendall $p = 0.004$) before reversing to a significant increase over 2014–2024 ($p = 0.043$), with the post-break rate of change exceeding twice the magnitude of the preceding decline and robust to the choice of break year (sensitivity sweep, 1997–2018).

Fig. 3. Observed trends in BFAI for 22 European countries, 1990–2024. Points show the annual BFAI of each country and the red line is the fitted linear trend; note the independent y-axis scale in each panel. Filled and open red triangles in panel headers denote confirmed and likely trends, respectively (up = increasing, down = decreasing). See Table 2 for full trend statistics.

413 **Model estimation of burnt forest areas**

414 The final predictor set retained after feature selection consisted
 415 of vapour pressure deficit (VPD_{year}), fire weather indica-
 416 tors (FWI_{3+_NDJF}, FWI_{4+_NDJF}, FWI_{5+_ONDJFM}, and
 417 FWI_{6_ONDJFM}), available cumulative water deficit (AWD_{0-40_sum_AMJJAS}
 418 and AWD_{0-40_sum_NDJF}), together with
 419 country as a categorical predictor and forest composition vari-
 420 ables represented by the shares of conifers and pines. Variable
 421 importance analysis identified annual vapour pressure deficit
 422 (VPD_{year}) as the dominant predictor of BFAI variability, fol-
 423 lowed by country-specific effects and forest composition vari-
 424 ables represented by the shares of conifers and pines (Figs 5).

425 Among the climate-related predictors, indicators of fire-weather
 426 severity (FWI) and cumulative soil moisture deficit (AWD)
 427 contributed substantially to model performance, highlighting
 428 the combined importance of atmospheric dryness, antecedent
 429 moisture conditions, and fuel characteristics. The relatively
 430 high importance of country as a predictor suggests that factors
 431 not explicitly represented by the climatic variables, including
 432 differences in fire management, land use, and reporting sys-
 433 tems, also play an important role in shaping burnt forest area
 434 outcomes across Europe.

435 The machine learning analysis revealed substantial varia-
 436 tions in model performance across the 12 algorithms tested

Table 2 Analysis of trends in the BFAI in 22 European countries (Country), showing projected tendencies (Trend), the slope and p value of the linear regression between the BFAI and Year; and the p values determined via the Mann–Kendall test.

Country	Trend	Slope	Lin. reg. p-value	Mann–Kendall p-value
AUT – Austria	Stable	-0.0001	0.721	0.842
BEL – Belgium	Likely decreasing	-0.0030	0.726	0.036*
BGR – Bulgaria	Stable	-0.0234	0.660	0.390
CHE – Switzerland	Likely decreasing	-0.0091	0.025*	0.140
CZE – Czech Republic	Stable	-0.0071	0.109	0.349
DEU – Germany	Stable	-0.0012	0.446	0.099
DNK – Denmark	Stable	-0.0031	0.533	0.917
ESP – Spain	Likely decreasing	-0.1100	0.026*	0.069
FIN – Finland	Stable	+0.0000	0.995	0.953
FRA – France	Stable	-0.0200	0.123	0.078
GRC – Greece	Stable	+0.0661	0.307	0.410
HRV – Croatia	Stable	-0.0244	0.678	0.379
ITA – Italy	Likely decreasing	-0.0737	0.064	0.021*
LTU – Lithuania	Decreasing	-0.0056	0.007**	<0.001***
LVA – Latvia	Stable	-0.0106	0.187	0.589
NOR – Norway	Stable	+0.0014	0.283	0.410
POL – Poland	Decreasing	-0.0395	0.005**	<0.001***
PRT – Portugal	Stable	+0.0293	0.921	1.000
ROU – Romania	Increasing	+0.0159	0.006**	0.003**
SVK – Slovakia	Stable	-0.0021	0.647	0.842
SVN – Slovenia	Likely decreasing	-0.0064	0.469	<0.001***
SWE – Sweden	Likely increasing	+0.0021	0.420	0.020*

Slope in $\text{ha kha}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}$. Decreasing/Increasing: both tests $p < 0.05$; Likely decreasing/increasing.: one test $p < 0.05$; Stable: neither significant. Significance: *** $p < 0.001$ ** $p < 0.01$ * $p < 0.05$

Fig. 4. Pan-European aggregate burnt forest area index (ABFAI; forest-area-weighted mean across 22 countries), log scale, 1990–2024. Piecewise regression with 95% confidence band; the dotted line marks the break-point (BP) at 2014. On-plot labels give each phase’s slope ($\% \text{yr}^{-1}$) and one-tailed Mann–Kendall significance (* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$).

Fig. 5. Relative importance scores of predictors retained after recursive feature elimination (RFE) using a Random Forest algorithm. Vapour pressure deficit (VPD_year) was the most influential predictor, followed by country, forest composition variables (conifers and pines), fire weather indicators (FWI), and available water deficit (AWD) metrics. Predictor definitions and abbreviations are provided in Table 1. Importance scores are unitless and indicate the relative contribution of each predictor to model performance.

437 (Fig. 6). The RMSE values for the calibration dataset ranged
 438 from 0.46 (Bagged Classification and Regression Trees) to 1.12
 439 (Support Vector Machine with linear and polynomial kernel),
 440 whereas the verification RMSE values ranged from 1.00

(Random Forest) to 1.09 (Elastic Net Regression). The close agreement between the calibration and verification performance across most models indicates good generalization capability without substantial overfitting.

The performance of the tree-based methods was consistently strong, with the Random Forest method achieving the best verification performance (RMSE = 0.84 for calibration and 1.00 for verification). Bagged Classification and Regression Trees showed excellent calibration performance (RMSE = 0.46) but higher verification error (RMSE = 1.04), suggesting some potential overfitting. Extreme Gradient Boosting performed well, with RMSE values of 0.97 (calibration) and 1.02 (verification), whereas Cubist Regression yielded RMSE values of 0.98 (calibration) and 1.05 (verification).

Linear and flexible regression methods showed moderate performance, with the Generalized Linear Model achieving RMSE values of 1.10 (calibration) and 1.02 (verification), respectively, while Elastic Net regression performed similarly, with 1.02 (calibration) and 1.09 (verification), respectively. Multivariate adaptive regression lines (MARS) showed comparable performance, with RMSE values of 1.09 (calibration) and 1.04 (verification).

The ensemble model (Fig. 7), constructed through stacked generalization, achieved the best overall performance, with RMSE values of 1.01 (calibration) and 1.02 (verification), as shown in Fig. 8. While the ensemble did not achieve the lowest individual RMSE values compared with those of some individual models (Random Forest had a RMSE of 1.00 for the verification dataset), it provided the most balanced performance across both datasets, which was considered advantageous for subsequent climate-scenario applications. The ensemble approach effectively combined the strengths of the different modeling approaches, with R^2 values of 0.79 and 0.80 for the calibration and verification datasets, respectively.

Analysis of the ensemble composition revealed that Support Vector Machine (Radial) contributed most heavily to the final predictions, accounting for approximately 46% of the ensemble weight (Fig. 8). Extreme Gradient Boosting was the second most influential component, contributing approximately 23% of the ensemble weight. Artificial Neural Networks collectively accounted for approximately 26% of the ensemble weight across three ensemble members, while Elastic Net Regression contributed approximately 5%. The presence of several model types within the final ensemble highlights the value of combining complementary machine-learning approaches to improve predictive performance and robustness.

The observed versus predicted plots (Figs 6 and 7) demonstrate that the models effectively captured the substantial variation in the BFAI across countries. Portugal consistently had the highest predicted and observed values ($\log(\text{BFAI}) > 3$), followed by Spain and Mediterranean countries. The lowest values were consistently recorded in Sweden and Austria ($(\log(\text{BFAI}) < 0)$), with the models accurately capturing this geographic gradient. The scatter around the 1:1 line was generally modest across

the prediction range, although some heteroscedasticity was evident, with larger residuals at higher BFAI values, particularly for extreme fire years in Mediterranean countries.

Model projection of burnt forest areas

The ensemble model was applied to project future BFAI values for Sweden, Czech Republic, and Italy, representing northern, central, and southern Europe, respectively, under the SSP2-4.5 climate scenario. Projections were generated using six global climate models (GCMs) for four future periods: 2030 (2015–2044), 2050 (2035–2064), 2070 (2055–2084), and 2085 (2070–2099). The projections reveal a consistent upward trajectory in BFAI across most climate models (Fig. 9), despite the historical success of fire management in maintaining stable burnt areas.

Substantial differences were evident among the three representative countries. Sweden consistently exhibited the lowest BFAI values, whereas Italy showed the highest values and the greatest spread among climate-model projections. Czech Republic occupied an intermediate position between these two climatic extremes. Despite differences in absolute values, the ensemble trends indicated increasing BFAI in all three countries. The magnitude of the projected increase was smallest in Sweden, intermediate in Czech Republic, and largest in Italy. Relative to the historical baseline, the ensemble trend increased only modestly in Sweden, whereas increases of approximately 40% and 75% were projected for Czech Republic and Italy, respectively, by the late 21st century.

The spread among GCM projections highlights climate-model uncertainty in future fire-risk assessments. Differences among models became more pronounced in later projection periods, particularly by 2070 and 2085, indicating increasing uncertainty toward the end of the century.

The projected changes were not strictly linear. Several country–GCM combinations showed stronger increases during the second half of the 21st century than during earlier projection periods, suggesting that climate-driven fire risk may intensify with continued climate change.

Discussion

Trends in burnt forest areas

Our analysis of burnt forest area, or more specifically, BFAI trends across 22 European countries from 1990–2024, reveals a contrast to global patterns of increasing wildfire activity (Jones et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2024) but supports other earlier global observations of burnt areas (Andela et al., 2017). Of the 22 countries analyzed, 13 showed no significant BFAI trend, while Lithuania and Poland demonstrated significantly decreasing trends, and Romania was the only country with a confirmed significant increase. A further six countries exhibited likely trends based on one significant test, suggesting a broader but not fully confirmed pattern of decline across temperate and

Fig. 6. Observed versus predicted values of log-transformed burnt forest area index (log(BFAI)) across 12 models, with their performance evaluated on both the calibration (open symbols) and verification (filled symbols) datasets. Each panel represents one model, showing predictions for all 22 countries using country-specific shapes and colors. The root mean square error (RMSE) is reported separately for the calibration and verification subsets. The dashed diagonal line indicates perfect agreement. Differences in performance across models highlight variations in generalizability and predictive accuracy.

Fig. 7. Predicted versus observed values of the log-transformed BFAI (log(BFAI)) for the final stacked ensemble model. Each point represents a calibration (open symbols) or verification (filled symbols) observation across the 22 countries, with distinct colors and shapes used for country differentiation. The diagonal dashed line indicates perfect agreement between the observed and predicted values. The root mean square error (RMSE) is reported separately for the calibration and verification subsets.

Fig. 8. Relative contribution of individual base learners to the final stacked ensemble model. Stacking coefficients were estimated using penalized regression, where the penalty parameter controls the amount of regularization applied to the model weights. A higher penalty shrinks coefficients toward zero, reducing the model complexity and mitigating overfitting. Each bar represents the stacking coefficient assigned to a model during the blending process, reflecting its influence on the ensemble predictions. Models with higher coefficients contributed more substantially to the ensemble.

543 Mediterranean Europe. Additionally, 16 of the 22 countries
 544 showed a negative regression slope, indicating a broadly declin-
 545 ing pattern of BFAI across the continent (Fig. 3, Table 2). These
 546 findings directly challenge the assumption that climate-driven
 547 increases in fire risk automatically translate to proportional
 548 increases in burnt area.

549 An absence of generally increasing BFAI trends, despite
 550 documented trends in fire-conducive weather conditions (VPD
 551 increased significantly in 10 countries, dead fuel moisture
 552 decreased in seven countries, and the annual FWI signifi-
 553 cantly increased in four countries), provides compelling evi-
 554 dence for the effectiveness of European fire management sys-
 555 tems. This apparent paradox demonstrates that technologi-
 556 cal and institutional improvements can successfully counter-
 557 act climate-driven increases in fire risk, at least within the
 558 European context. These findings align with previous observa-
 559 tions in Mediterranean Europe (Turco et al., 2016). The effec-
 560 tiveness of European fire management has been attributed to
 561 several factors, including improved early warning systems (San-
 562 Miguel-Ayanz et al., 2013), enhanced suppression capabilities
 563 (Fernandes et al., 2016), and strategic fuel management through
 564 prescribed burning and silvicultural treatments (Fernandes and
 565 Botelho, 2003; Moreira et al., 2011). Additionally, socioeco-
 566 nomic changes, including rural depopulation and agricultural

abandonment, have altered fire regimes across Europe (Pausas 567
 and Keeley, 2014; Moritz et al., 2014). 568

The geographic pattern of these trends is noteworthy. The 569
 confirmed declines in Lithuania and Poland correspond to the 570
 Baltic and Central European fire regimes, whereas Romania’s 571
 confirmed increase may reflect distinct land-use dynamics 572
 and management trajectories in southeastern Europe. Among 573
 Mediterranean countries with historically high fire activity, 574
 Spain and Italy exhibited likely decreasing trends, while no 575
 significant trend was detected in Greece, Croatia, or Portugal, 576
 consistent with the interpretation that management invest- 577
 ments have broadly stabilised fire outcomes even under high 578
 climate pressure. These findings suggest that both high-risk 579
 Mediterranean and lower-risk temperate countries have devel- 580
 oped effective fire management approaches across diverse 581
 European climatic and ecological conditions. Similar patterns 582
 have been documented in Portugal, where Fernandes et al. 583
 (2014) reported that despite increasing fire weather severity, 584
 the burnt area has decreased because of improved firefighting 585
 capacity and strategic landscape management. The European 586
 Forest Fire Information System (EFFIS) has documented this 587
 continent-wide trend, with Turco et al. (2016) reporting an 588
 overall decrease in burnt area across southern Europe from 589
 1985–2011 despite increasing fire danger ratings. 590

Fig. 9. Projected burnt forest area index (BFAI) for Sweden, Czech Republic, and Italy, representing northern, central, and southern Europe, respectively, based on the ensemble model under the SSP2-4.5 climate scenario. The colored points represent BFAI values for the historical baseline period (1985–2014) and four future 30-year periods centred around the years 2030, 2050, 2070, and 2085 across six global climate models (GCMs). The dashed line indicates the mean observed BFAI for the reference period 1990–2024. The solid gray curve represents a LOESS-smoothed trend across future projections. Despite differences among countries and climate models, an overall increase in projected BFAI is evident under future climatic conditions.

These results collectively demonstrate that European fire management has been remarkably effective at decoupling fire outcomes from climate pressure over the past three decades. The stability or decline in burnt areas across the most European countries, despite significant increases in fire-conducive weather, provides compelling evidence that institutional and technological investments in fire prevention, early warning systems, and rapid suppression can successfully mitigate climate-driven fire risk. This success is particularly notable given that such management effectiveness has been achieved across diverse climatic contexts, from Mediterranean fire-prone regions to temperate Central Europe.

However, the pan-European aggregate trend indicates that this decoupling may not be unconditional: the post-2014 reversal in the ABFAI (Fig. 4), with the increase outpacing the earlier decline, suggests that climate-driven fire pressure has begun to exceed the compensating capacity of current management systems rather than merely catching up with it.

Model performance and climate drivers

The ability of the ensemble model to explain 79% and 80% of the variance in the calibration and verification datasets, respectively, indicates that climate variables, together with country-specific effects, explain most burnt-area variability across Europe, even after decades of technological advancement. This high explanatory power validates our central hypothesis that climate-based models retain robustness for fire risk assessment, despite evolving management practices. Our results are consistent with large-scale fire modeling studies that have demonstrated strong climate control of fire activity globally (Archibald et al., 2013; Forkel et al., 2019) and regionally in Europe (Bedia et al., 2015; Turco et al., 2018). The inclusion of country as a categorical variable proved crucial in addressing systematic differences in fire management effectiveness, forest composition, topography, and socioeconomic factors. During recursive feature elimination, country consistently ranked among the most important predictors, indicating that substantial variation in BFAI remains associated with country-specific characteristics beyond the climatic variables considered here. This finding is consistent with previous work by Bistinas et al. (2013) and Andela et al. (2017), who emphasized the importance of human factors and regional characteristics in global fire models.

The dominance of VPD in the variable-importance analysis is ecologically plausible because VPD integrates the combined effects of temperature and atmospheric moisture demand, thereby directly influencing vegetation drying and fuel flammability. Compared with individual fire-weather metrics, VPD may better capture the cumulative atmospheric conditions that predispose forests to large fire events. Its strong predictive value therefore reinforces the view that increasing atmospheric dryness is a key mechanism linking climate change to burnt-area dynamics across Europe (Seager et al., 2015; Williams et al., 2020; Nagavciuc et al., 2024).

The ensemble approach provided robust and balanced performance (RMSE = 1.01 for calibration and 1.02 for verification), with nearly identical predictive accuracy in both datasets. Such consistency is particularly valuable for operational applications where model stability across different conditions is essential (Solomatine and Ostfeld, 2008). Among the individual models, Random Forest achieved the lowest verification RMSE (1.00), demonstrating the effectiveness of tree-based methods for capturing complex fire–climate relationships. Other nonlinear machine-learning approaches, including Extreme Gradient Boosting, Support Vector Machines, and Artificial Neural Networks, also performed well. The strong performance of these methods relative to simpler linear approaches suggests that fire–climate relationships involve complex interactions and threshold effects that cannot be fully captured by linear models. Random Forest methods have proven particularly effective for fire prediction across diverse ecosystems (Oliveira et al., 2012), whereas ensemble methods are being increasingly applied to fire risk assessment because of their robustness and ability to combine complementary model structures (Zhang et al., 2019; Kondylatos et al., 2022). The consistent performance of tree-based methods across both the calibration and verification datasets suggests that these approaches effectively capture the nonlinear nature of fire–climate interactions without overfitting and thus provide more confidence for their application in climate scenarios.

The final predictor set was dominated by annual VPD, cumulative AWD metrics, several FWIs, forest composition variables, and country-specific effects. The importance of FWI-derived predictors aligns with established fire science principles and previous European fire studies, where FWI has been extensively validated as a predictor of fire danger and burnt area variability across Europe (Viegas et al., 2000; Good et al., 2008). The retention of AWD variables further highlights the importance of cumulative drought stress and soil moisture deficits for shaping fire activity, while the prominence of conifer and pine shares reflects the well-established role of vegetation characteristics in determining fuel availability and fire behaviour.

Although DFMC was not identified as an important predictor by the Boruta feature-selection procedure and was therefore excluded from the final predictor set, previous studies have shown that dead fuel moisture, particularly in fine fuels with short time lags, plays a critical role in fire ignition and early fire spread (de Dios et al., 2015; Nolan et al., 2020). Its exclusion from the final model likely reflects the substantial overlap in information captured by other drought- and fire-weather-related predictors, including VPD, AWD, and FWI variables. More generally, the varying importance of different temporal aggregations (annual versus seasonal) suggests that optimal prediction strategies may require regional customization, consistent with the findings of Bedia et al. (2018) and Turco et al. (2019) regarding regional fire seasonality patterns in Europe.

The composition of the final ensemble model provides additional insight into the nature of climate–fire relationships.

Support Vector Machine (Radial), Artificial Neural Networks, and Extreme Gradient Boosting together accounted for approximately 95% of the ensemble weight, whereas the contribution of Elastic Net Regression was comparatively small. These machine-learning approaches are particularly effective at capturing nonlinear relationships and interactions among predictors, suggesting that burnt forest area is not simply a linear function of individual climatic variables. Instead, fire activity appears to emerge from complex and nonlinear interactions among atmospheric dryness, accumulated drought stress, forest composition, and country-specific factors.

Future fire risk projections: insights from selected case study countries

The application of our ensemble model to future climate scenarios provides important insights into the potential trajectory of fire risk under continued climate change, while also highlighting both the strengths and limitations of climate-based fire projections. The generally consistent upward trends projected across most climate models and all three representative countries suggest that climate pressure may increasingly challenge the historical effectiveness of fire management in maintaining stable burnt areas. These findings are particularly noteworthy given that most analysed countries exhibited stable or declining historical trends in burnt forest area during the observational period, suggesting that maintaining current levels of fire-management effectiveness may become increasingly challenging under future climatic conditions.

The projected increases are consistent with the post-2014 reversal in the observed ABFAI, suggesting that the climate signal may already be emerging despite the continued effectiveness of fire-management systems.

The substantial spread among GCM projections highlights a critical challenge for fire-risk planning. Differences among climate models became more pronounced in the later projection periods, particularly by 2070 and 2085, indicating increasing uncertainty toward the end of the century. Nevertheless, the overall direction of change was generally consistent across models, with most projections indicating increasing fire risk under future climatic conditions. This uncertainty is consistent with broader climate-projection studies in Europe, where future changes in temperature, precipitation, and drought-related variables show considerable inter-model variability (Coppola et al., 2021; Skalák et al., 2025).

While climate-scenario projections were generated for all analysed countries, results are presented for Sweden, Czech Republic, and Italy as representative examples of northern, central, and southern European conditions. These examples likely capture broader patterns expected across European regions with contrasting climates, forest compositions, and fire-management systems. However, several important limitations must be acknowledged. First, the assumption of static fire management effectiveness may not reflect adaptive capacity or potential technological improvements over the 21st century.

Second, the projections do not account for potential changes in land use, forest composition, or demographic patterns that could influence fire regimes (Senf and Seidl, 2021). Third, although projections were generated for multiple SSP scenarios, only SSP2-4.5 is presented here. Higher-emissions pathways would likely result in more pronounced increases in fire risk.

Implications for adaptive management

The success of European approaches, particularly in countries showing confirmed decreasing trends (Lithuania and Poland), demonstrates the effectiveness of prevention-focused strategies over reactive suppression approaches. This aligns with economic analyses showing positive cost-benefit ratios for European fire management investments (Pacheco and Claro, 2021). The stable or declining trends observed across the majority of European countries suggest that targeted investment in comprehensive fire management infrastructure yields significant returns. Key components include early warning systems (San-Miguel-Ayanz et al., 2013), rapid detection networks, strategic fuel management (Fernandes et al., 2016), and coordinated suppression capabilities.

The success of European fire management appears to stem from continent-wide coordination through systems such as EFFIS, combined with country-specific adaptation of strategies to local conditions. The post-2014 reversal in the pan-European ABFAI trend described above underscores that this balance between management capacity and climate pressure is already shifting within the observed record, not only in projected future scenarios. As fire risk expands to traditionally low-risk regions, knowledge transfer from Mediterranean countries to temperate regions becomes increasingly important (Tedim et al., 2018). Our projections indicate that these investments must be sustained and potentially expanded to maintain effectiveness under increasing climate pressure. Moreover, the consistency of the upward trend across climate models suggests that adaptation is essential rather than optional.

Methodological insights

The robust performance of our ensemble model in both historical analysis and projection applications demonstrates the value of climate-based statistical approaches for long-term fire risk assessment. However, the projection exercise also reveals the importance of incorporating management adaptation scenarios in future modeling efforts. Coupling our statistical approach with scenarios of management system evolution could provide more realistic projections for policy planning (Moritz et al., 2014). The contrasting projections for Sweden, Czech Republic, and Italy illustrate how future fire-risk trajectories may differ across the European climatic regions. Nevertheless, all three examples showed increasing BFAI trends under future climatic conditions, suggesting that climate change may place increasing pressure on fire-management systems across a broad range of European environments. Expanding projection analyses to

additional countries, particularly those representing different climatic conditions, fire regimes, and management capacities, and incorporating alternative climate and management scenarios would provide a more comprehensive assessment of future fire risk across Europe.

Conclusions

This study demonstrates the robustness of climate-based statistical models for predicting burnt forest area across diverse European conditions. Our ensemble modeling approach, which combines multiple machine learning algorithms, explained 79% and 80% of the variance in burnt area for the calibration and verification datasets, respectively, indicating that climate variables, together with country-specific effects, explain most fire-activity variability despite decades of management improvements. Tree-based methods proved most effective at capturing the complex, nonlinear relationships between climate drivers and fire outcomes, whereas the ensemble approach provided superior stability and generalization across different conditions.

The modeling results reveal that European fire management has successfully offset climate-driven increases in fire risk over the past three decades. Despite increasing fire-conducive weather conditions, most countries have shown stable or decreasing trends in burnt forest area, with Lithuania and Poland demonstrating significant decreases. This finding challenges the assumption that climate-driven fire risk automatically translates to increased burnt area, highlighting that effective management systems can decouple fire outcomes from climate pressure. However, a pan-European break-point around 2014 marks a reversal from this decline to an increasing aggregate trend, indicating that climate pressure has begun to outpace management capacity within the observed record, not only in future projections.

When applied to future climate scenarios, the ensemble model projects moderate but consistent increases in burnt area across the representative northern, central, and southern European countries by the end of the century. These results suggest that although European fire-management systems have successfully limited climate-driven increases in burnt area during recent decades, maintaining this effectiveness may become increasingly challenging under continued climate change.

However, important limitations include the country-level analysis scope and static management assumptions in projections. Future research should incorporate dynamic management scenarios and expand to multiple countries and emission pathways.

Ultimately, this study validates climate-based ensemble modeling as a robust approach for fire risk assessment while demonstrating that sustained investment in prevention-focused fire management can help sustain effectiveness, even as intensifying climate pressure increasingly tests its limits.

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Data and code availability. The analyses presented in this article can be fully reproduced using the R code, input datasets, and supplementary materials provided in the GitHub repository: <https://github.com/MilanFischer/BFAI>. All analyses were conducted in R version 4.5.2 (R Core Team, 2025), primarily using the tidyverse, tidymodels, stacks, caret, and Boruta packages.

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